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CONTRACTUAL AND PROFESSIONAL STATUS OF TEACHERS IN RELATION TO COLOMBIAN CURRICULUM DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

This scientific article presents the results of research derived from a doctoral study focusing on the Colombian educational system's curriculum. The conclusions relate the contractual modality through which teachers enter, endure, and graduate from the teaching profession in the Colombian education system to the motivations, guarantees, and difficulties with which they approach the curriculum. This is represented by salary disparity, evaluative dissimilarity, meritocratic distinction, and difference in stability of position, diversity of decrees governing them, inequality in teacher professionalization, and other factors. Using a qualitative methodology based on an interpretive paradigm and an educational ethnography modality developed over four consecutive years, the instruments of in-depth interviews, participant observation, reflection workshops, documentary tracking, and fieldwork were used to understand how teachers in a specific Colombian educational context – I. E., El Playón de Medellín—address the various phases of curricular development (self-curriculum, prescription, proscription, presentation, molding, action, evaluation, realization, and curricular concealment). This study intends to propose generalizable inductive reasoning by examining how contractual modalities influence Colombian teachers.

KEYWORDS: Contractual And Professional Status Of Teachers In Relation To Colombian Curriculum Development.

1. INTRODUCTION

From the eighteenth century to the present, the teaching profession in Colombia has undergone significant changes and historical periods. Depending on the time period, there have been different conditions for entering the teaching profession, professional status within the educational guild, and opportunities for teacher professionalization. During the republican period, the regime of teachers in the public sector was guided by a Professionalization Statute that created favorable or unfavorable conditions regarding their contractual, motivational, and professional status within the teaching profession. This may have directly caused achievements, tensions, or mistakes in the curricular development established by the Colombian educational system.

This research article is based on findings from doctoral-level research in which the stages of the curricular development of Colombia's Chair of Peace were analyzed in the context of the El Playón Educational Community in the city of Medellín. Through a qualitative methodology consistent with an interpretive paradigm, it was possible to analyze the phases of self-curriculum, prescription, proscription, presentation, molding, action, evaluation, realization, and curricular concealment in this group of 660 students.

A complete study of the teaching staff in the El Playón de Medellín Educational Community (50 teachers) allowed us to investigate the link between their professionalization trajectories and contractual status and their theoretical and practical capacities, motivations, and pedagogical professionalism in the pre-, interactive, and post-curricular phases. This opens the field to propose recommendations for each phase of the curriculum from a process-oriented perspective.

2. METHODOLOGY

According to Hernández et al. (2014), a qualitative methodology "focuses on understanding phenomena by exploring them from the participants' perspective in a natural environment and in relation to their context" (p. 358). The participants are part of the El Playón Educational Community, an institute offering formal education at preschool, elementary, middle, and high school levels. Located on Calle 125 Number 51D - 12 in the El Playón de los Comuneros neighborhood of Medellín, Colombia, the institute is urban, official, and mixed, operating under calendar A. It provides comprehensive services in the morning and afternoon to 660 students and their families from Commune 2 of Santa Cruz de Medellín and

surrounding neighborhoods and municipalities (Akros, 2025; SIMAT, 2025). This report is based on research conducted on the "teaching establishment," which served this population from 2022 to 2025. A total of 50 professors participated in the study, and all signed informed consent forms allowing the publication of research articles derived from the doctoral research in which they participated. The qualitative approach leverages an "interpretive paradigm," emphasizing understanding of processes, where theory becomes a "reflection" of and from practice, intentionally favoring the acquisition of practical knowledge (Ricoy, 2006).

Considering the theoretical-conceptual foundation of the curriculum as a process of cultural knowledge construction (Cuervo, 2014; Gimeno, 2007), reference is made to San Fabián (1992), who states: "Since education is a cultural process by which children and young people learn to act appropriately as members of a society, it makes it a particularly suitable environment for educational ethnographic research" (p. 18), ratifying the modality of educational ethnography (Álvarez, 2008) with emphasis on teachers of the squad. This offers congruence between 1) the theoretical-conceptual categories, 2) the methodology, 3) the paradigm and 4) the research modality.

With this ethnographic-educational approach, the "school culture" of EI was investigated. El Playón (Runge, 2019, p. 28), linking it to the practical reflection of the curriculum developed by teachers, which according to Jackson (1968), Grundy (1994), Gimeno (2007), Cuervo (2014), Loveless and Williamson (2017), Uribe and Cuervo (2020), presents the preactive, interactive, postactive phase – prescription, proscription, presentation, molding, action, evaluation, realization, curricular concealment, and self-curriculum –.

Analyzing this curriculum as a process, in relation to the contractual modalities through which teachers enter, remain, and leave the educational system, allows us to propose educational ethnography. The basis of educational ethnography lies in investigating how different human actors construct and reconstruct social reality through interaction with other community members. For this, it is essential to consider their interpretations of the reasons for their actions and the situation in general, according to Angus (1986), Erikson (1986), Hammersley (1997), and Smith (1987).

This educational ethnography of the curricular process, under the segregating approach of contractual modality and professional status through which teachers enter, endure, and leave their

teaching work in the public sector of the Colombian teaching profession, was proposed as "circular-simultaneous" (Álvarez, 2008, p. 5). It proposes a design of the methodological moments of institutional culture as follows.

2.1. Negotiation and access to the Field

Approach and dialogue with the rector of the campus, to grant permits and necessary access, as well as with professors interested in participating in the research. "By negotiating access, we get hold of a very valuable type of information, and in a way, that negotiation is a permanent process. The first moments are as crucial as the rest of the moments" (Sanchiz & Cantón, 1995, p. 129).

2.2. Immersion in Fieldwork

In this phase, four (4) techniques for collecting information were used, which were analyzed to be taken to triangulation of perspectives:

- Tracking and documentary analysis: both of decrees and laws at the national level, as well as of institutional documentation predominantly of the teaching establishment.
- Participant observation: of teachers' encounters with the learner, and of the interactions between these teachers and directors, administrators, staff with various functions and members of the context.
- In-depth interview / dialogic interview with teachers: allowing a dialogue rather than an interview, since for two authors such as Velasco & Díaz de Rada (2006), "its relevance lies in the fact that it is woven on dialogue and provides a discourse that is alien to the subjects of study" (p. 34). With the participating teachers, the in-depth interviews were recorded in audio format, then they were transcribed in editable word processor format for PC, and both inputs were processed and saved through an encryption system with BitLocker.
- Reflection workshops: with teachers as protagonists of interaction with other levels and

actors of the educational scenario.

2.3. Data Analysis

According to Rodríguez et al. (1996), "the polysemic nature of the data, their predominantly verbal nature, their unrepeatability, and the large volume of data usually collected during research make analysis difficult and complex" (p. 201). They proposed a scheme for constructing meanings through the selection and organization of data via a filter. The various stages of the curriculum were analyzed to understand the praxis of researched nodal categories. This was done by constructing "explanatory categories" from the discourse of the individuals involved. The aim was to understand how teachers approached the curricular phases according to their contractual modality and professional status in their careers as teachers in the Colombian public education system. An analysis of the information was carried out, allowing for a triangulation of subjects, spaces, times, methods, and experts.

2.4. Preparation of the Ethnographic report

Frequent and cross-sectional editing process with the findings found during 4 consecutive years of research. An academic production was not proposed at the end of the data collection process, but on the contrary, uninterrupted, periodic and simultaneous work, which finally facilitated: an "ethnographic-educational analysis of institutional culture, influenced by a processual curriculum, related to the contractual modality and professional status of entry, durability and graduation of teachers".

Finally, it is clarified that the information collected arises within the framework of the development of a doctoral thesis research, where the data were collected during a total of 4 consecutive years, which can be projected in the following synthesis scheme:

Figure 1: Methodological scheme of the ethnographic-educational analysis of institutional culture.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Admission, permanence, status and professionalization in the teaching career in Colombia

In the history of the teaching profession in Colombia, five periods are identified crossed by relevant milestones, allowing a journey that goes from 1776 to 2025, where it is understood that, in its beginnings, teaching was considered a "trade", and entering the work in Colombia during the eighteenth century, depended on the blessing of a priest, who determined whether the professor in question was virtuous, without meaning that he or she became an employee of the State, since this link with the public treasury was only achieved at the end of the nineteenth century (Bayona-Rodríguez & Urrego-Reyes, 2019).

The church had a great influence on the process of admission of teachers in Colombia, since between 1946 and 1953 a baptismal certificate and a certificate of good conduct were required by the parish priest to belong to the teaching profession (Quiceno, et al.,

2004), and politics also exercised great control over teacher interviews through letters of recommendation from politicians. where, after the enactment of the Statute of Teacher Professionalization (Decree 1278, 2002), public competitions were brought forward (CNSC, 2025), mitigating through aptitude tests to hold career rights, the religiosity and/or politicization with which human resources were managed —although the figure of "provisional teacher" still exists (Decree 1278, 2002, p. 3-4), (DAFP, 2022).

However, in the educational institutions of the Republic of Colombia —such as the I. E. The Playón de Medellín, a universe complex with members divided into 7 estates, currently not only do teachers who entered under the conditions of Decree 1278 of 2002, or the logics of provisionally, work, but there are still teachers who enter under the guidance of Decree 2277 of 1979. In-depth interviews and other fieldwork techniques with the 50 teachers who made up the census or complete population study of the teaching profession yielded results regarding the entry, permanence, status and professionalization

processes of their teaching profession.

With these teachers who occupied an official position between the years 2022 - 2025 in the I. E. In the Playón de Medellín, in-depth interview/dialogic interview techniques were developed (Robles, 2011), reflection workshops (Covarrubias, 2013), participant observation (Fernández, 2009) and documentary tracking (Tancara, 1993). Twenty-two (22) teachers performed their educational function as provisional teachers, seven (7) teachers were governed by Decree 2277, and twenty-one (21) held career rights linked by merit-based competition according to Decree 1278.

On entry into the teaching career: based on information collated by the four technicians, 24 teachers stated that their admission to the profession had some relationship with political, administrative and/or religious influences; it was revealed that all the teachers governed by Decree 2277 agreed with this statement –recalling his private admission between September 1979 and June 2002–, and that 17 of the 22 provisional members also supported this assertion. The rest of the teachers – 21 by competition and 5 provisional – assured that their entry depended exclusively on their own merit and the aptitudes/attitudes required by the public competition at the national level to which they applied – any of the calls between 2002 and 2022 (MEN, 2024) – or the application to the application that brings together the resumes of teachers interested in entering the official education service in definitive vacancies with appointment provisional (SistemaMaestro, 2025).

The statements made by the teachers investigated regarding the entry into the teaching career identify the historical milestone of the first call for a teaching merit competition (Law 715 of 2001, Decree 3238 of 2004, Decrees 4235 of 2004, Decree 3333 of 2005) as a turning point to consider a before and after of the process of admission to the teaching profession. The following reference points are considered.

1) The period prior to June 2002, considered by them as the most favorable for any applicant, since the number and distribution of places throughout the national territory – including districts, cities and demographically dense towns – was much greater; for the levels of preschool, basic primary, basic secondary, middle and intermediate education they could be presented as pedagogical baccalaureates; in rural areas that are difficult to access (Concept 044741 of 2023) simple bachelors were appointed as teachers, and for indigenous communities a person could be appointed simply for being bilingual –without much additional requirement– (Decree 85 of 1980;

Soto, 2013); Political, religious, and/or experiential letters of recommendation were decisive or exerted great weight when considering a candidate; there were fewer "contenders" who fought for a place, because there were fewer graduates due to the lack of numerous institutions where educators were professionalized for the work.

2) The period after June 2002, considered by them as a time when the requirements were tightened, since as the various calls for teaching merit competitions have been completed, many places in Colombia have already been awarded to candidates – considerably decreasing the availability especially in densely populated districts, cities and municipalities; specific profiles are required for university graduation – or post-baccalaureate according to the level to which one aspires to practice the profession, being higher as one rises in the levels of institutionalized education; The number of applicants for the same position has risen considerably in the face of the number of institutions that offer pedagogical training, however, the path is not exclusive to professionals from Faculties of Education and Pedagogy, but professionals from multiple basic nuclei of knowledge such as administrative sciences, agricultural sciences, engineering, social sciences, arts and humanities can apply. Political science, among others.

Parallel to this, nine (9) of the professors involved with the research had entered the private sector years ago and had developed professional experience in that niche; however, they migrated to the public sector when they considered "better contractual opportunities and/or job stability". Two (2) of them develop teaching hours (Concept 047311 of 2023) with the private sector at the same time as being teachers linked to the Colombian teaching profession under Decree 1278, and despite acknowledging that they prefer the contractual panorama of the public sector, their interest is to create work history and experience with said business sector, in addition to being an economic aid of biweekly remuneration, in addition to their monthly salary.

On permanence and status in the teaching career: the 7 teachers governed by Decree 2277 are the ones who have the longest time of service in the official education sector, ranging from 39 years of uninterrupted service, the oldest teacher in the I. E. El Playón, and 25 years old. This group manifests security and stability in their professional work, evidencing special protection for being already retired – deciding to work until the age of forced retirement, which is 70 years old (Law 1821 of 2016) – or being in the administrative situation of "pre-

pensioners", enjoying enhanced job stability (Judicial Branch Superior Council of the Judiciary, n.d.). Parallel to them, the 21 teachers who hold career rights for having passed the entrance competition convened by the National Civil Service Commission, also manifest security and stability in their jobs, and although in this group of teachers there are officials who have recently passed a probationary period and were recently enrolled in the teaching rank, there is a high sense of stability in the workplace; their greatest annual concern is failing the performance evaluation, or incurring in a very serious offense according to Internal Disciplinary Control (Public Function, 2022), which could mean retirement from service. Finally, these two previous sets, as well as that of the 22 provisional ones, come in unison to consider the figure of provisionality as totally unstable, unpredictable and subject to the will of the immediate boss (rector), nominating entity (Ministry of Education), or even technical variables such as educational supply and demand, number of students enrolled in SIMAT, curricula and curricular changes, teaching positions projected for the school year, among other factors.

In the fieldwork developed for this research, which covered a total of "4 consecutive years", it was evidenced –with a participant observation technique– that, unlike professors with career rights, no provisional completed that same time of uninterrupted work in the I. E. El Playón; There were provisional teachers who were linked to the educational institution for a short period of time – months or even weeks – which was in line with what was stated in the in-depth interviews, where the majority tendency was to consider the provisional teacher as a fairly changing job position, subject to the transfers of teachers with career rights. or the employment of teachers who come to carry out a probationary period within the framework of merit-based competition.

However, in addition to this job stability/instability (permanence), there were also differences in monthly economic remuneration and permanent evaluation (status), depending on the contractual modality to which the teachers belong. On the side of monthly economic remuneration, all the teachers of Decree 2277 expressed in an interview, a felt disadvantage in relation to the teachers "winners of merit competition", since according to Decree 0596 of June 03, 2025, the maximum remuneration –in Colombian pesos– to which this first group of teachers in mention, can reach, corresponds to \$6,758,592 per month, which is practically half of the maximum amount that a

teacher who wins a competition and with career rights governed by Decree 1278, corresponding to \$13,293,724, performing similar educational functions (Decree 0596, 2025, p. 1-10).

The arguments of the teachers of Decree 2277 are based on the fact that, despite fulfilling the same educational functions, having three or four decades of seniority in the teaching profession, and having more practical experience in the position, they continue to earn in the last grade of the teaching ladder, approximately half of what they earn in their respective final grade of the scale, teachers belonging to Decree 1278 by competition. In another sense, those teachers of Decree 1278 by competition, argue that, despite understanding this salary difference in the last grade of the scale, very few reach that level, they must hold a Doctorate or Postdoctoral degree to reach that hierarchical rank – a factor that is not a requirement for the maximum grade of Decree 2277 –, they must earn "at least and in the best of scenarios" three ECDFs to reach the top level of the ladder, and in addition, this ladder is constantly frozen for them, so that promotion evaluations end up being developed every three years or five years. The high monetary percentages that teachers benefit from under Decree 2277 in terms of social benefits – health and pension – are also compared to the low percentages and harsh requirements of teachers under Decree 1278 (MinEducación, 2023).

What the total of 50 teachers investigated do agree on is that the greatest salary disadvantage is borne by the "provisional" teachers, since both teachers with career rights governed by Decree 1278, and those of Decree 2277, are registered in the teaching ladder, being paid equitably according to their university degrees. the time of service they have been linked to the Colombian State and the great opportunity to "move up by passing evaluations". On the other hand, provisional professors are not registered in any scale, so that, despite having doctoral or postdoctoral degrees, they are already prohibited from moving up in any hierarchical system, through the passing of a test of a diagnostic-formative nature. It does not matter if a provisional professor has 10 or 20 years of uninterrupted service, or has a doctorate or postdoctorate from a prestigious university faculty; in any case, it is impossible for him to be promoted by passing a formative evaluation, due to the fact that he is not registered in the teaching hierarchy because he does not win a merit-based competition (Decree 1278 of 2002), or he will not be promoted, if he is not old and was hired under the guidelines of Decree 2277 of 1979.

The fact of being subject to permanent evaluation,

or not being so, generates differentiation of "status" within the profession, according to their research versions, being the professors of Decree 2277 who recognize that by not applying the Annual Performance Evaluation (Decree 3782 of 2007), they feel more confident to unionize, to demand rights within their workplace, to fully exercise academic freedom, and therefore, to develop the curriculum of the areas under their responsibility with greater autonomy. The teachers of Decree 1278 by competition, consider that they are at a lower level of said "status", since they are evaluated, their functions and tasks are constantly monitored with documentary and/or testimonial evidence (MinEducación Guía 31, 2008) and could be qualified as failed, so they feel less freedom in the development of curricula and transversal projects. as well as being more reluctant to unconditional participation in the face of the calls of the unions, since they perceive that the immediate bosses or nominating entities could "settle accounts" through a negative rating for the teacher.

Finally, temporary teachers are perceived as having the lowest level of status. Like teachers under Decree 2277, they are not subject to an annual performance evaluation. However, they are implicitly evaluated based on comments or results that reach their immediate superiors. The consequence is not a negative quantitative evaluation in an annual evaluation, which could result in an improvement plan. Rather, they may be transferred without consultation to another educational institution or withdrawn from service to make room for a requested teacher with career rights.

On professionalization in the teaching career: in this sense, the general perception that is evident in the total of 50 teachers researched is that qualification is useful in 2 ways. The first is related to professional self-preparation to grow in the disciplinary field of belonging and in the epistemological knowledge that one possesses; the second - being quite transcendental for the teachers under study - with a utilitarian, administrative and economic function, since it is a fundamental prerequisite for promotion in the teaching ranks, either under the figure of Decree 2277 or 1278.

The highest educational degree held by some of the 7 investigated teachers who work under the figure of decree 2277 has been that of "specialist" - previously being, either pedagogical bachelor, education technician, educational technologist, normalists, graduate or non-licensed professional - it being understood that, with this title of specialist, it is possible to reach the last grade of their respective

remuneration scale of the profession - in addition to other requirements, as well as those of seniority. In the development of the fieldwork, they expressed their reluctance to develop master's, doctorate and/or postdoctoral studies, arguing that they no longer required additional degrees to be promoted, and that this would represent a lot of time, effort and money not to see economic remuneration in the medium or long term - making explicit the economic reason for their decision, and that this reason weighs more than an epistemological or academic process of personal qualification-. Among the 22 provisional teachers, 9 were non-licensed professionals, 11 pure graduates and 2 were professionals with master's degrees; When asked about their intention to continue their professionalization process, the 20 professors without postgraduate studies (post-undergraduate) expressed their reluctance to develop a specialization, master's, doctorate or post-doctorate, unless in the medium or long term, a merit-based competition was called and they effectively passed it, since this would ensure that the degree would have economic remuneration. Finally, of the 21 professors with career rights by competition, none holds a doctoral or postdoctoral degree, only 1 professor is developing this study in a foreign university through virtual methodology, stating that it is cheaper in monetary and temporal terms than a face-to-face national degree, despite the fact that she is not certain that said foreign degree will be validated in Colombia (MEN, 2019), so he does so for reasons of promotion in the teaching ranks. When asked about professionalization and teaching qualification with these postgraduate levels - doctorate / postdoctorate, the answer is that "it is not worth it" the time, money and effort invested, for the subsequent remuneration that this title has in the teaching ladder, so the reasons are oriented to an economic issue, and the epistemological-academic motivations are not transcendental.

Finally, it is perceived that teachers with career rights, either under Decree 2277 or 1278, are presented with greater opportunities for professionalization and teacher qualification through public or private calls such as SAPIENCIA, in contrast to provisional teachers, who are presented with fewer opportunities, since there are no specific programs for them. Possibly because of the latent possibility that they will be promptly removed from the educational service.

The comparison of the in-depth interviews with the other information collection techniques shows that belonging to one or another set of teachers deployed in this research article, explicitly generates

in Colombian legislation and implicitly in the institutional culture "a professional segregation and teaching status", which can have an impact on the curricular development of the areas, subjects, projects and/or chairs that are assigned to the teachers themselves, according to their particular histories of professionalization, and the type of contract they hold before the Ministry of National Education and the Territorial Entity to which they are attached. This becomes a pillar of analysis for the various phases of curricular development in a processual key.

3.2. Influence of contractual and professional teacher status in the preactive, interactive and postactive Colombian curricular phase

The cataloguing of a certain group of teachers, either within the group of provisional teachers, linked under Decree 1278, or with career rights according to Decree 2277, generates an explicit and/or implicit segregation of "contractual and professional status" that influences attitudes, dispositions and behaviors in the curricular approach of Colombian institutionalized education. According to the author Philip W. Jackson, we can distinguish the preactive, interactive and postactive phase of teaching (Jackson, 1968), just as in Gimeno (2007) we speak of the phase of prescription, presentation, molding, action and curricular evaluation. This research compiled important aspects of these processual views of the curriculum and teaching work, to offer results that link the contractual and professional status of teachers, with the approach of the various phases, understood as a warp of connections.

3.3. On the prescription, proscription, presentation and curricular molding, as a pre-active phase:

The structuring axis of education systems, which responds to centralized regulatory frameworks, understood as prescribed curriculum (Macías & Cabrera, 2025); school textbooks, didactic educational resources, physical and/or virtual material –presented curriculum– (Vargas, 2017); translations and adaptations that are carried out both of the laws and of the resources presenting the content –molded curriculum– (García-Rubio, 2018); as well as finally, those knowledges that are discarded and annulled at the time of the design of the practice –proscribed curriculum– (Cuervo, 2017); are approached in a differentiated way, according to the contractual and professional status of the specific teacher who comes to play the role of

developer of these curricular phases.

The need for high professional qualification to move up in the teaching ranks, the fact of being subject to permanent evaluation under the contracting territorial entity, and the graduation of updated educational programs, revealed that the teachers who won merit-based competitions under Decree 1278 declare greater willingness and legislative-pedagogical updating to translate the laws of the prescriptive curriculum and the physical/virtual materials of the curriculum presented. to their architectures of practice – curricular molding, without annulling transcendental parcels of knowledge, due to lack of academic-experimental capacity.

On the other hand, having graduated from universities or colleges of the highest education system decades ago, having professionalized up to the undergraduate level –or in the highest case, specialization–, not being subject to annual quantitative evaluation, and being able to move up the ladder due to seniority, causes a state of stagnation in the process of qualification and professionalization of teachers in the teaching group governed by Decree 2277. This reflects an unmet demand for the use of Information and Communication Technologies for the architecture of their practices in curriculum modeling, the proscription of important fragments of the curriculum for the learner –due to lack of theoretical-practical knowledge of epistemology to be transmitted, and the outdated didactic resources to be implemented. for monopolizing inputs that in past decades were considered indispensable in the teaching work – such as the typical school textbook – in contrast to the technological advances of contemporary times.

In the end, the inability to predict their own stability in the workplace, the impossibility of ensuring permanent monitoring of the instructive-evaluative process of the student in the development of their curriculum, and the contractual and emotional insecurity generated by this panorama of intermittency, makes the group of "provisional" teachers translate the laws and educational materials in a less rigorous way than the teachers linked by meritocracy. as well as that their participation in the processes of curriculum shaping –especially the group ones–, is superficial, since the constant institutional transfers, cause there to be permanent interruption in the processes, and force them to be frequently changing pedagogical models, visions and institutional missions and even work teams/colleagues, according to the factual reality of

each of the educational institutions where they have to join involuntarily, even for periods as short as months or weeks.

3.4. On curricular action and concealment, as well as self-curricula in the interactive phase:

The hidden curriculum, as defined by Torres (1998), is understood as the values, beliefs, and attitudes that are implicitly evident in the customary environment of institutionalized school culture. Provisional teachers who perceive their place in the teaching profession to be uncertain have been shown to experience a negative impact on their curricular action (Valbuena, 2008), (Jiménez, 2010), and their self-curriculum (Loveless and Williamson, 2017). It is evident that the teaching staff in question recognizes the precarious nature of their professional standing, which is perceived to be contingent upon the approval or disapproval of their immediate supervisor. Consequently, they adopt a cautious approach in their pedagogical practices, opting for activities that are less prone to criticism and risk. This, in turn, restricts their creativity and fosters a more conservative demeanor, both in their own instructional methods and in the activities they design for their students.

The pedagogical staff's self-curriculum, both for themselves and for their students, is characterized by its sporadic nature. This is largely attributable to the unpredictability of job stability, which often leads to their departure or transfer from the educational institution. This phenomenon hinders the development of a strong cultural connection and an emotional bond with the specific educational community within which they function.

Conversely, teachers' perceptions under Decree 2277 have been linked to a sense of confidence in their roles, attributed to the perceived influence of an institutional hidden curriculum. This confidence is further bolstered by the perception of sufficient academic freedom to develop activities and tasks that are immune to criticism, or at least, exempt from annual quantitative evaluation processes. As demonstrated in Research 2, there are two distinct cases in evidence. The optimal environment for the development of curricular action and self-realization is first identified. Subsequently, an examination of anarchy in teaching practice, the proposal of activities/tasks, and the development of the self-curriculum of the teacher and his/her students is conducted.

Teachers who are governed by Decree 1278 yet hold career rights by meritocracy occupy an intermediate point of perception. The hidden

curriculum fosters a perception of greater stability among the former teachers compared to the group of provisional teachers. However, it also imposes more stringent control and monitoring measures than those observed in the group of former teachers under Decree 2277. In this context, the curricular action—defined as activities and tasks—is developed in a manner that aligns academic freedom with documentary and/or testimonial evidence, which is to be demonstrated in the permanent process of annual performance evaluation that this group of teachers must pass. The development of the self-curriculum exhibits a less intermittent pattern than that observed in the group of provisional teachers, yet it is more controlled than that seen in the group of permanent teachers. This is due to the alignment of the self-curriculum with the demands of their permanent evaluation and the needs of the educational service.

3.5. On curricular evaluation and implementation, as a post-active phase:

Both the assessment of the activities and tasks that students develop around the course of their curriculum (Brovelli, 2001), and the evaluation of this curricular construction (Grundy, 1994), and the complex short-, medium- and long-term effects apprehended by teachers when experiencing the curriculum and institutional culture—curriculum carried out—(Gimeno, 2007); They manifest themselves in a diversified way, according to the status—contractual condition—and the level of professionalization of the particular group of teachers analyzed.

The results obtained in fieldwork for 4 consecutive years, reflect that only 18.1% of provisional teachers within the census or complete population study of the teaching establishment in the research, could last in the Educational Institution El Playón de Medellín, to develop a complete process of follow-up to the evaluation and promotion of a student cohort within the establishment; evidencing that in terms of assessment of activities, tasks and transit through the basic and secondary education of the student, these teachers are cut off from the processes. The same happens with their participation in the evaluation of the construction of the curriculum at the institutional level, where their constant transfers or withdrawals from the educational system, generate cuts in the continuity of processes, even those that are macro and point to the construction of the IEP, pedagogical model, SIEE, coexistence manual, curricular meshes, area plans, etc. pedagogical projects and institutional chairs.

This configures a profound effect in the short, medium and long term – curriculum carried out – both in teachers and in the educational community, where this group of teachers is considered unstable, and their contribution to the evaluation process is not fully considered, since it is thought that their follow-up will be cut off at some point in the school year.

Teachers governed by Decrees 2277 and 1278 by competition, perceive that their follow-up to processes, assessment of the student and contribution to the institutional curricular construction is much more stable and lasting than in the group of provisional teachers. As there are teachers with more than three or four decades of permanence in the teaching profession – even since the officialization of the Educational Institution as a public establishment (Institución Educativa El Playón, 2025) – and having very remote possibilities of being transferred or removed from the position, it is perceived that their opinions, contributions, contributions and participations are quite significant and entail the plus of durability. As with the provisional ones, the curriculum generated short, medium and long-term effects; however, on this occasion, the perception of students, families, the community and themselves, is of great authority in the evaluation at the institutional level and the relevant weight of their contributions for having a long career in the institution, thus generating a differentiating bias due to their status and professional career.

4. DISCUSSION

A comprehensive analysis of four consecutive years' worth of results, in-depth interviews, observations from fieldwork, documentary tracking, customary perceptions of the El Playón de Medellín Educational Community (among other inputs), reveals that the contractual and professional status of teachers has a significant impact on the curricular development of Colombian institutionalized education, whether positive or negative. The implementation of the profession in accordance with the principles outlined in Decree 2277, Decree 1278 as a teacher with career rights, or within the framework of provisionality, exerts a significant influence on the development of each phase of the preactive, interactive, and postactive curriculum.

In this sense, the curricular prescription phase is defined as "the set of contents that an educational system aspires to transmit and that is generally declared in official documents of public circulation" (Ferrer, 1999, p. 1). The curricular presentation phase is understood as a translator and interpreter of the

laws in instructions for teachers, where "the most decisive means is represented by textbooks" (Rodrigues, 2013, p. 88). These phases are used in a diversified way, according to the contractual status and the professionalization path of different groups of teachers. Teachers who, according to their decree, require greater and permanent qualifications to move up in their ranks—as in the case of teachers of Decree 1278, who hold doctorates and post-doctorates—demonstrate a greater willingness and theoretical management for the treatment of the laws and academic contents of these two specific curricular phases. Teachers belonging to Decree 2277 are more reluctant to update didactic materials that present the curriculum. This is due to the fact that they were promoted based on seniority and graduated decades ago from programs that are no longer offered for teacher training. As a result, they do not possess contemporary qualifications to move up in their ranks. They prioritize the classic school textbook in the knowledge society. They ignore recent legislation, even voluntarily annulling it (curricular proscription). They are not teachers subject to annual evaluation, so this does not affect them as a group with rights acquired by seniority. Runge (2019) found that provisional teachers do not have the same opportunities for teacher qualification and professionalization as teachers with career rights. Provisional teachers do not have access to programs and financial aid to pursue their master's, doctorate, and postdoctoral degrees. As a result, they generally consider their preparation to be less theoretical and practical. This means that they are less able to translate the macro phases of the curriculum into the planning and actual practice in the classroom.

The subsequent step entails the "decoding—interpretation, meaning, recreation, reinterpretation—of ideas, conditions, and available practices" that pertains to the molded curriculum (Marrero, 2010, p. 223). This is in conjunction with the curriculum in action, which is "focused on the classroom teacher as a leading actor who develops at the operational level, often with critical thinking and strategic action" (Castillo, 2015). Additionally, the evaluated curriculum signifies "entering into the analysis of all the pedagogical practices that take place in the institution" (Brovelli, 2001, p. 107). It is important to note that this approach is unequally implemented, contingent on the contractual modality and the professional "status" held by the teacher in question.

The group of provisional teachers faces significant challenges in participating in the curricular

evaluation phase. Their frequent inter-institutional transfers or removals from the position hinder the ability to provide consistent monitoring of students. This situation hinders their capacity to establish robust cultural and institutional foundations, thereby impeding their contribution to the evaluation of curricular development. In contrast, teachers with career rights, who have demonstrated stability in their positions for decades, possess the professional authority to engage in such evaluations due to their long-term tenure. In another sense, teachers governed by Decree 2277 transform their extensive experience in teaching into a "habit," leading to infrequent alterations in educational practices. Conversely, the guild led by Decree 1278 demonstrates a greater propensity to translate this phase of the curriculum "into a constantly modified action." This discrepancy can be attributed to the demands of the annual performance evaluation, the academic-pedagogical trends of their studies, and the institutional contextual realities, which compel them to engage in perpetual professional development. Finally, the group of teachers who entered the teaching profession on the basis of meritocracy – by competition – self-perceive as having a significant number of tools with which to shape the curriculum. For this reason, they approach this phase with ease, supported by their postgraduate degrees and the constant training they receive in favor of their promotion in the ranks. However, the barrier to teacher qualification – voluntary and involuntary – for both the most senior teachers and provisional teachers causes a reduction in the range of possibilities for evidence-based models of educational practices.

The prevailing experience of the hidden curriculum, in conjunction with the experimentation inherent in the curricular implementation phase, serves as foundational elements in elucidating presumptions and behaviors that fortify institutional culture, in alignment with the conceptualization of "professional status," which is concomitant with the contractual modality that the teacher maintains in a particular manner.

It is imperative to acknowledge the notion that the hidden curriculum functions as a pivotal instrument in the acquisition of the prevailing norms, values, and social relations that are embedded within and perpetuated through quotidian routines within educational institutions and teacher training centers (Trujillo et al., 2025, p. 3). The curriculum produced exerts a profound influence on factors such as professional socialization (Gimeno, 2007), manifesting in diverse and intricate short-, medium-

, and long-term effects. The segregation of Colombian public teachers into at least three distinct contractual categories of professional development has been demonstrated to engender multifaceted repercussions on their work, thereby underscoring the necessity for an examination of the curricular approach to the fundamental core of knowledge to which they are affiliated.

Consequently, within the context of the institutionalized educational day-to-day, stereotypes of "professional status" are perpetuated, engendering a medium- and long-term impact on teachers. These stereotypes are often characterized by the attribution of labels such as "provisional," "competitive," or "with career rights by seniority." This predisposition influences their pedagogical and practical educational work, impacting the manner and quality with which they translate prescriptions and proscriptions, as well as curricular presentations. It also influences their work's molding and execution, and the potential for developing curricular evaluations of students and contributing to the pedagogical and visionary model of the institution, given their degree of job stability.

The final factor of stability has been demonstrated to influence the development of self-curricula (Loveless & Williamson, 2017) and professional qualifications. A significant number of provisional teachers experience stagnation in their professionalization process due to a lack of economic opportunities that their counterparts perceive. These teachers do not perceive a sense of purpose in the development of high-level programs, such as doctorates and postdoctoral studies. As they are not enrolled in a teaching career ladder and are unable to ascend to the highest level within a hierarchical remuneration system, they do not perceive economic remuneration to be sufficiently relevant to motivate them to invest the time, money, and effort required to study these issues.

In this manner, the disparity in the contractual models through which teachers enter, endure, and graduate in the Colombian teaching profession, as well as the discrepancy in economic remuneration, guarantees of permanence in the job, requirement of permanent evaluation, conditions of registration and promotion in the teaching rank, among other factors, influences different attitudes, aptitudes, presumptions, dispositions, and behaviors of these teachers, in relation to their approach to the multiple phases of the Colombian curriculum, which is regarded as a process – self-curriculum, prescription, presentation, molding, action, evaluation, realization, concealment, and curricular proscription.

The aforementioned factors have a considerable impact on the performance of teachers in relation to their role in transmitting knowledge as a cultural heritage. This phenomenon is often referred to as "curriculum in institutionalized education." The curriculum in question has the potential to be homologated in other educational systems in Latin America or internationally. This is due to the existence of similar scenarios in which the teaching workforce is segregated by laws and decrees that govern their professionalization, promotion, job stability, and other conditions differently. This is a highly probable scenario and a subject of great research interest.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The contractual modality through which an individual enters, remains in, and exits the Colombian teaching profession (public sector) determines a specific set of requirements for assuming the position (e.g., competition, seniority, etc.), the degree of stability and permanence in the union (e.g., years worked), the monthly salary earned, whether or not the individual is enrolled in a national teaching rank, whether the individual is exempt or subject to permanent annual evaluation, the economic remuneration for promotion or relocation, and even the manner in which social benefits are granted (e.g., health and pension), among other factors.

The influence of contractual status on curricular variables is a subject of interest in this study. The concept of curricular variables is understood as a processual construction with a cultural tinge, and it is influenced by institutional customs that are deeply rooted in educational communities. In this research, the Community of the I. E. El Playón de Medellín is used as an example. Within this community, imaginaries are created about the professional status, prestige, and authority that a teacher possesses, according to his or her unique trajectory in the Colombian educational system.

The phases of self-curriculum, prescription, proscription, presentation, molding, action, evaluation, realization, and curricular concealment are approached with a differential approach. If one enters and works in the teaching profession according to the logic of Decree 2277 of 1979, the provisions of Decree 1278 of 2002 by competition, or under the conditions of the figure of provisionality, then one may approach these phases in a certain way.

Teachers governed by Decree 2277 move up the ladder without the need for the ECDF (MinEducación, 2018) as an instrument consistent

with the Competency Assessment referred to in Article 35 of Decree 1278 (Decree 1278, 2002, p. 8), being able to reach their last hierarchical grade holding a specialist degree – not a master's degree, nor a doctorate – and accumulating "many" years of seniority in the service. This predisposes that in the phase of curricular molding, action and evaluation, "what has served in those past decades of teaching work" continues to be done –restricting renewal–, and that the translation of the prescription and presentation phase is basic, since there is little incentive for contemporary academic professionalization and renewal, and the custom leads to using the same didactic resources of previous decades –prioritizing the typical school textbook, in contrast to technological advances. The hidden curriculum and carried out at the institutional level, labels them as the oldest teachers, and precisely for this reason, as broad connoisseurs of the institutional context.

Teachers governed by Decree 1278 with career rights—by competition—perceive that they have adequate tools to translate the phase of prescription, presentation, and curricular molding into practice. This is due to the fact that they hold master's degree studies and advance doctorate/postdoctoral studies, which are fundamental prerequisites to move up in their teaching career. These studies are related to the pedagogical and academic updating necessary to address these curricular phases. However, when they arrive at the curriculum in action and evaluated, they sometimes work cautiously. This is because, unlike teachers of Decree 2277, they are subject to annual evaluation of permanent performance. If they fail this evaluation on two or more occasions, it could result in their retirement from the position. This set is indicative of the development of self-curriculum, owing to its experience in the academic world with high postgraduate studies. The hidden curriculum is implemented at the institutional level, and it is used to label teachers who have won competitions and who hold high university degrees. However, these teachers act with greater caution in their educational practice because they are subject to the constant approval or disapproval of their immediate superiors and nominators. This is in contrast to the teachers of Decree 2277. Although the teachers of Decree 2277 have greater stability than the group of provisional teachers, they are also subject to greater scrutiny.

Finally, the hidden curriculum, implemented at the institutional level, has the effect of labeling provisional teachers as the most unstable in the workplace. This is due to the fact that they are subject to the dispositions and wills of the immediate bosses

or appointing entities. As a result, provisional teachers are intermittent in the phase of curricular molding, action, and evaluation. This is due to the fact that they cannot ensure follow-up for consecutive years to a cohort of students or to the contribution of an institutional curricular proposal projected in the medium and/or long term. The phases of prescription, presentation, and self-curriculum present obstacles to their optimal development. Unlike teachers with career rights, the economic opportunities for permanent qualification are not as affordable. In addition, these opportunities do not represent such a clear stimulus because teachers without career rights are not yet enrolled in any teaching ladder. As a result, it is impossible for them to move up because they have not passed a merit-based competition.

In conclusion, the proactive, interactive, and post-

active curricular phase exhibits discrepancies that align with the stratification implemented among public educators in the Colombian teaching profession with regard to their contractual modalities. It is imperative to acknowledge the variations that may influence the curricular process, given the unique characteristics inherent to each educator. A discernible tendency of approach and factual conditions has been observed to exert an influence on the curricular phases. This tendency is attributed to the Decree 2277, Decree 1278 by competition, or the group of provisional teachers. The various conditions of entry, permanence, salaries, evaluation, promotions, social benefits, and so forth, have a positive or negative impact on the self-curriculum, prescription, presentation, molding, action, concealment, realization, proscription, and curricular evaluation.

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